

THE EMANCIPATING EFFECT OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Education in its real sense is an emancipator of self and prejudices which successively unites the mankind. Hence it demands reverence, respect, honour, devotion and dedication. It also expects high standard of culture and gentlemanliness. The turmoil in the world and the degradation of the countries is the result of lack of proper education. The recent education system creates person of intelligence but not person with humanity. This very reason made world just a Warfield than of brotherhood. The only panacea to these prevailing problems is nothing but the proper education. To emancipate the oppressed, education in proper sense should be spread to the whole humanity drop by drop. Now the world doesn't face much of illiteracy but now the world is full of qualified illiterates with respect to manners and humanity. Thus education should be for emancipating the inequality and to build a better world of tolerance, righteousness and understanding.

Keywords: the panacea, emancipation of the oppressed, unity of mankind, educative communication.

Introduction

Education in its real sense is an emancipator of self and prejudices which successively unites the mankind. Hence it demands reverence, respect, honour, devotion and dedication. It also expects high standard of culture and gentlemanliness. The turmoil in the world and the degradation of the countries is the result of lack of proper education. The recent education system creates person of intelligence but not person with humanity. This very reason made world just a Warfield than of brotherhood. The only panacea to these prevailing problems is nothing but the proper education. To emancipate the oppressed, education in proper sense should be spread to the whole humanity drop by drop. Now the world doesn't face much of illiteracy but now the world is full of qualified illiterates with respect to manners and humanity. Thus education should be for

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The Gravity of Education

“Regard man as a mine rich in gems of inestimable value. Education can, alone, cause it to reveal its treasures and enable mankind to benefit therefrom”.

Education should fulfill not only the intellectual considerations but also the ethical thoughtfulness to be a true citizen, for education is the rudimentary factor in shaping a true citizen. In today’s young minds are the promise and guarantee of tomorrow lie- the seeds of future society- thus rearing the young seedlings with perfect sunshine and water is a necessity to be taken care of. This care can only be possible through education, which his/her parents, teachers and society should uphold.

Imbibing the qualities to be needed for a right human can be inculcated through a propitious communication. Thus our communication should be always educative and enlightening rather than of rumors and untruth. A favorable education in all its right sense can promise the world a better culture of emancipating the downtrodden to the mainstream with all its necessities. Education and educative communication alone can uplift the one who is driven to the wall. The significance of education, in any era, any society can never be nullified. How education can transform the lives of human is a noteworthy issue which all the educators and society seeking for. The present era is noted for its science and technological advancement but at the same time decline of principal ethical concerns. But, where all these ethical disarrays start from? Yes. It is high time to ponder upon.

When human advancement heightened in the field of science and technology, the control over his thought been redirected to technology- smart phones, tabs, and numerous to count on. But education in its purest sense should mean to cultivate the good in man. Gandhiji rightly pointed it out, “By education I mean an all-round drawing of the best in child and man in body, mind, spirit”. But today’s education system fulfills the first part alone, consciously forgetting the mind and spirit- even the education system emphasizes the development of cognitive, affective and psychomotor, the inculcation of these domains have given way to the consumerism and selfishness. The present generation are more of Machiavellians than of a true server to the society.

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An educated person is one who has the following characteristics

- An educated person realizes the human nature and improves his ability to establish, maintain, and improve lasting relationships.
- An educated person establishes rapport with others easily and behaves appropriate to the situation in order to tackle and maintain the bond between them.
- An educated person knows what is right and wrong way of handling things.
- An educated person treats all equally with human consideration.
- An educated person knows how to cooperate and collaborate effectively with others.
- An educated person will be wiser than knowledgeable or informative. etc

These are some of the pivotal differences between a knowledgeable person and an educated person.

Peters’ Criteria of Education and being educated

Peters rejects the attempt of defining education by saying, no definition can fully incorporate the real meaning of education. Thus he came up with the idea of formulating three criteria to which may match the processes of education. Any process that does not satisfy these criteria, will be vain and cannot result in the production of an educated man. The criteria are as follows,

- i. Education implies the transmission of what is worthwhile to those who become committed to it;
- ii. Education must involve knowledge and understanding and some kind of cognitive perspective, which are not inert;
- iii. Education at least rules out some procedures of transmission, on the grounds that they lack willingness and voluntariness on the part of the learner.

Thus it is important for a person to be knowledgeable and educated. The academic education or qualification may take you to heights but it may not make you the real human. The spot light of education system should be on, how to make children educated in the real sense not just to furnish their curriculum vitae with mere material achievements. An individual who acquires competence in some limited area may not qualify to be described as educated.

Emancipate the materially oppressed

Today's World, as we can witness, is full of injustices. Oppression of the women folk by domineering male counterparts is not a rare happenings. From age to age, the suppression of

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women folk is being a common incident of no wonder. It should be taken away and can only be possible through the right education. The care system, class system and so on to cou, creates a huge gap between man and man. these types of inequalities can only be remediated through an education which is a proper fit for today. The intrinsic and instrumental value of education also should be made available to all from elementary to the higher educational as to emancipate the people from slavery of different kinds.

Emancipate the oppressed self

Emancipation means to “Set free, especially from legal, social, or political restrictions” as per the dictionary meaning. We might have gone through several historical events showcasing the victory of the oppressed through revolts or civil wars. But the real emancipation a human has to get is from his own self- the selfish motives. Education in its real sense is that which must free you from all the inequalities than just showing off.

The so called educated (by academic qualification not in reality) people’s prophecy about equality and equity still considers their own wives or daughters as their subordinates. The mentality of the person should be emancipated first, and then to the society it will spread over.

Emancipate from superstition and prejudice to build Unity on Earth

Swami Vivekananda in his Chicago Parliament of religion in the year 1893 stated that “if there is ever to be a universal religion it must be one....whose sun will shine upon the followers of Krishna and of Christ, on Saints and sinners, alike, which will not be Brahminical or Buddhist, Christian or Mohammedan, but the sum total of all these and still have infinite space for development....and whose whole scope, whose whole force, will be centered in aiding humanity to realize its own, true divine nature”.

This quotation throws light on to the importance of having unity of all religion which is possible only through true education which frees man from superstition and prejudices. Removal of prejudices helps people to be objective in their perspective.

“The heaven of true understanding shineth resplendent with the light of two luminaries: Tolerance and Righteousness”. Inculcation of tolerance and righteousness is possible only through removal of superstition and prejudices which in turn builds a better society and a united world of joy.

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Emancipate through educative communication

Communication is a cyclical process among the three protagonists namely Sender, Message and Receiver. When the message is educative, the receiver gets educated. As Aristotle rightly pointed out, a message should involve Ethos, Pathos and Logos in order to mentally and emotionally to move the receiver. An educated person- literate or illiterate- should communicate with optimism and the reinforcing nature will unite the mankind and develop equality among all.

The present era with pessimism and destruction is the result of subjective communication- a biased communication with prejudices and expectation kills the virtue and man doomed to death war and disunity.

Education should make man to open his mind to new optimistic arena and of a broader perspective which is the rudimentary difference between a just knowledgeable and an educated person. An educated person- the so called ‘Cultured Man’ will uphold the values necessary for mankind which is the part and parcel of the universe.

It is rightly accepted that there are three kinds of education: ‘material’, ‘human’ and ‘spiritual’; the ‘material education’ focuses on progress and development of the physical aspects-of body, of comfort and ease. ‘Human education’ means the attainment of culture and progress which is the essential distinction among human and animal. Next the epochal one, the ‘Spiritual education’ which consists of divine perfection that is what the paramount vision of any true educator which lacks in the present society.

The universe is in need of such educators who fulfill these three education at the same time to emancipate the oppressed of different arena. Thus it is the duty of each educator to be unquestionably and undoubtedly perfect or nearing perfection in all respect. Unless, she/he cannot be a true educator but just an ‘Information Giver’ whereas the students merely an Information Receptor’. It is high time to start it with the teachers to transform the prevailing circumstances of the world by moving the young minds to build a better universe.

Conclusion

A world embracing education is the only remedy to an emancipated and free world. Till the moment we embrace such an education, no changes in the world to unite human race will be possible. Educated person only can change the present condition of turmoil in any section, whether it be the changes in education system or it be the changes in political affairs. We need the rightly

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educated persons but not just some knowledgeable intellectuals.

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